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Master of Arts in Nursing

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**Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma and Burnout among
Nurses in the Emergency Department of Selected Tertiary Hospitals in
Laguna**

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ABSTRACT

AIM: To describe the level of awareness and determine the level of risk of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among emergency department nurses in selected tertiary hospitals in Laguna and its correlation to demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment.

METHOD: This study used an exploratory correlational research design to explore and determine the level of awareness of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among nurses working in the emergency department of selected tertiary hospitals in Laguna. The research utilized exploratory surveys and questionnaire such as the Professional Quality of Life Scale Version 5 (ProQOL) by Stamm (2012).

RESULT: Among 129 nurse respondents from the emergency departments of selected tertiary hospitals in Laguna, majority were working in private hospitals than public hospitals. Most of them were 20 – 29 years old, female, and mostly single. Majority of them have worked as a nurse and as an emergency room nurse for 0 – 5 years. The respondents worked for 32 hours or more per week and rendered overtime work for more than 16 hours or less. They also worked extra shifts of more than once per month. Given this work schedule, the respondents rarely engaged in physical activity. Furthermore, the respondents reported that they have a supportive work environment and colleagues that demonstrated positive attitude towards work.

CONCLUSION: Nurses in the emergency department of selected tertiary hospitals in Laguna had average levels of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. The researcher also concluded that there were significant relationships among compassion fatigue and hospital sector, parent, relationship status, and positive

attitude. Therefore, nurses who worked in private hospitals, who were single, childless, and with colleagues that demonstrated a positive attitude towards work had a significant relationship to compassion fatigue. This conclusion was similar to the findings for vicarious trauma and burnout. The study also showed that age and years of experience as a nurse had a significant relationship between vicarious trauma and burnout. Therefore, 20 -29 years old nurses and those with 0 – 5 years' work experience were significantly related to vicarious trauma and burnout.

Chapter I

The Research Problem

Introduction

The emergency room department faces different kinds of patients daily such as trauma patients, individuals who are near death, and those involved in unforeseen events. Nurses are exposed to a wide range of stressors including unpredictable work conditions and potential violence. Therefore, they must possess both general and specific knowledge about health care and illnesses in order to provide quality care. Besides these, other requisites to providing quality care are extensive knowledge in emergency medical treatment, the ability to use critical thinking, and good decision making skills. Even the most experienced nurses can be confronted with a complicated task that makes them vulnerable to a wide range of stressors. Both professionals and healthcare providers may experience emotional and physical exhaustion known as compassion fatigue that leads to vicarious trauma and burnout overtime as they continuously work in a fast-paced environment with a constant demand for quality care and combined with other trigger factors. Even though there is an appropriate intervention on compassion fatigue available for the nurses, they must also be able to increase their self-awareness and recognize the signs and symptoms of compassion fatigue for early prevention and to balance their work-life condition.

Several studies have found that the emergency room department has nearly eighty-six percent (86%) moderate to high compassion fatigue as opposed to other hospital locations (Hooper, Craig, & Janvrin, 2010). Consistently, a nurse exposed to human suffering and the intensity of a patient's traumatic experience lead to

compassion fatigue according to Petleski (2013). In fact, a cross-sectional study in 2016 concluded that empathy may be a risk factor for compassion fatigue while self-compassion may be a protective factor. Therefore, teaching self-compassion and self-care skills is an important intervention in reducing compassion fatigue. A resident doctor conducted a study on prevalence of compassion fatigue among residents, fellows, and nurses in Philippine General Hospital last October 2015. Twenty five percent (25%) of the respondents were highly at risk of having compassion fatigue. Nineteen percent (19%) were nurses working in the emergency room department. Those who handled more than twenty (20) patients per day showed that compassion fatigue was significantly associated (Casi, 2015). In this study, the researcher cited Stamm (2010) who proposed that in the professional quality of life, compassion fatigue has two elements, namely, vicarious trauma and burnout. According to Bouchard (2016), compassion fatigue is a phenomenon commonly conceptualized as the combined negative impact of burnout and vicarious trauma. Compassion fatigue may either lead to burnout or vicarious trauma when left unresolved.

The purpose of the research was to describe the level of awareness about compassion fatigue and determine the level of risk of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among Filipino nurses working in the emergency department (ED). The research also aimed to determine compassion fatigue's correlation to demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment in selected tertiary hospitals. The study used the ProQol tool by Stamm (2012) and questions about their thoughts on compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

The researcher observed that there were limited studies discussing compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among Filipino nurses working in the emergency room. Subsequently, most of the research studies published on the subject were about nurses working in the intensive-care unit. The researcher wanted to focus on the nurses' quality of life while working as an emergency room department nurse and recommend if there was a need to increase the nurse's awareness of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout that they may experience. As a nurse who has been working in an emergency room department for most of her career, the researcher wanted to expound and contribute knowledge about the emergency department.

This study served to bridge the gap for nurses who work in the emergency room department, compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. In addition, this research informed emergency room department nurses on how to recognize, prevent, and identify the coping mechanism methods of the three variables. Not only emergency nurses will benefit from this study but also the hospital administrators who need to understand how compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout affect the quality of treatment for patients and how to determine, manage, and prevent these from being experienced by nurses. The framework selected to guide this research was Stamm's Professional Quality of life. It included the elements of Professional Quality of Life that illustrate compassion fatigue which leads to vicarious trauma and burnout.

Statement of the Problem

There are limited research studies and references made in the Philippines regarding Filipino nurses, Filipino nurses in the emergency room setting, and compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout in Filipino nurses. Several studies published mostly discuss nurses in the intensive care unit and dialysis department.

The researcher aspired to determine and explore the health and quality of life among nurses working in the emergency room department, their level of awareness about compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. As the old adage goes, prevention is better than cure and this study aimed to help administrative leaders to become aware of these afflictions and assist in determining, managing, and preventing such stressors from affecting the nurses. According to the Department of Health, the country is experiencing scarcity of nurses, a high turnover rate in hospitals, and compromised quality care due to the ratio of nurse to patient. Knowing and increasing the nurses' awareness about these topics will help prevent developing stressors and eventually increase staff retention. Therefore, the research viewed this important information to prevent and recognize the signs and symptoms of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout. Awareness of the effects of the three variables is the key for the nurse's well-being.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study was to describe the level of awareness and determine the level of risk of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among emergency room department nurses and its correlation to demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment.

The specific objectives of the research study were:

1. To determine the level of the following among emergency room nurses

- a. Compassion fatigue awareness
 - b. Vicarious trauma awareness
 - c. Burnout awareness
2. To determine if there was a significant relationship between compassion fatigue and the following variables
- a. Demographic data
 - b. Work environment
 - c. Client environment
 - d. Personal environment
3. To determine if there was a significant relationship between vicarious trauma and the following variables
- a. Demographic data
 - b. Work environment
 - c. Client environment
 - d. Personal environment
4. To determine if there was a significant relationship between burnout and the following variables
- a. Demographic data
 - b. Work environment
 - c. Client environment
 - d. Personal environment

Significance of the Study

The results of the study will convey beneficial information to the following:

Nursing Practice

This study will impart information to the nursing society in relation to the role of nurses as educators and counselors in helping other nurses prevent compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma or burnout and acquire compassion satisfaction. In addition, the study will motivate the nurses to heighten and strengthen their understanding and awareness of how to recognize, prevent, and identify the methods of coping mechanism of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

Nursing Education

The study will serve as a good reference of an evidenced-based practice that may be used in teaching not only for nurses but also for practitioners and health care providers. Future nurses may use this study as their baseline and guideline concerning nurses and compassion to their profession.

For Future Researchers

Presently, there are limited studies done regarding compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among nurses in the Philippine settings. The findings of the study may serve as a baseline data for developing a program to improve and balance work/life condition among emergency room nurses and all health care providers. This may also contribute to future studies of nurses. In addition, the researcher wanted to distinguish factors affecting compassion fatigue and the intervention. Therefore, this study will alleviate the nurses' predicament in their compassion fatigue and increase their compassion satisfaction.

For Nursing Administrators

While the study is timely, there are other factors that may affect compassion fatigue, such as demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment that differ in the public and private institutions where the nurses are working. These should also

be taken into consideration. This study will serve as an eye opener for the management to address awareness of compassion fatigue and increase compassion satisfaction rate. Not only emergency room department nurses will benefit from this study but also the hospital leaders who need to recognize how the variables affect the quality of treatment for patients and how to determine, manage, and prevent compassion fatigue among nurses.

Scope and Delimitation

The area of study was limited to emergency rooms in selected tertiary hospitals in the province of Laguna, Philippines. Respondents of the study only included nurses working in the emergency room department and excluded nurses from other specialized areas such as the operating room department, the intensive care unit, and the dialysis ward. The inclusion criteria for the nurses in the study include those who work in a hospital regardless if it is a public or private institution, and those who have worked for six months and beyond. Exclusion criteria of the study include nurses from Level I and Level II hospitals and those who have worked for less than six months since they have minimal exposure to the area being studied. The study also included the demographic data of the respondents such as age, gender, relationship status, and if they are a parent, years of experience in the emergency room, years of experience as a nurse, number of working hours per week, number of shifted work hours, number of extra shift work hours, and physical activity.

Operational Definition of Terms

Tertiary Hospital

- A departmentalized hospital that provides particular forms of treatment, surgical procedure, and intensive care. Clinical services provided include general medicine, pediatrics, obstetrics, surgical gynecology, tertiary clinical laboratory, secondary level radiology, and pharmacy (DOH Administrative Order no. 2005-0029, 2005).

Compassion Fatigue

- Compassion Fatigue is the state experienced by helping people in distress; it is an extreme state of tension and preoccupation with the suffering of those being helped to a degree that it can create vicarious trauma and burnout for the helper.

Vicarious Trauma

- It is a work related, secondary exposure to extremely or traumatically stressful events. A transformation in the self of a trauma worker or helper caused by empathic engagement with traumatized patients and their reports of traumatic experiences. It is a special form of countertransference stimulated by exposure to the client's traumatic experiences. It is characterized by disrupted spirituality or a disruption in the trauma workers' perceived meaning and hope.

Burnout

- From the perspective of research, it is one of the elements of compassion fatigue. It is associated with feelings of hopelessness and difficulties in dealing with work or in doing your job effectively. This can reflect the feeling that your efforts make no difference, or can be associated with a very high workload or a non-supportive work environment.

Emergency Department Nurse

- Nurses working in the emergency room as a regular staff for more than six months. They care for patients with medical illnesses including stroke and myocardial infarctions. Emergency nurses also care for people suffering from traumatic injuries. They encounter diverse patient population. An emergency department nurse may likewise care for a mentally ill person in crisis or a young person suffering from drug overdose. Emergency room nurses also provide care to abused children and babies

with ear infections. They work in a wide variety of settings. Some nurses working in large medical centers specialize in providing care to trauma victims.

Work Environment

- Work environment is described as the surrounding condition in which an employee functions. It can refer to physical conditions such as the resources used by the nurses to provide the quality of care. Examples of these are computers, beds, cardiac monitors, blood pressure monitors, pulse oximeter, oxygen tanks, and so on. It can also be social interactions in the workplace such as with peers, colleagues, subordinates, and managers.

Client Environment

- Client environment refers to the environment that the nurses encounter daily while on duty or the so-called "patients". Client satisfaction towards the care rendered by the nurses, their behavior, the level of toxicity of the patient, and noise is also part of the client environment.

Personal Environment

- The personal environment is within oneself. The essentials of personal environment are health and safety such as personal refuge and a place to escape stress.

Shift work

- Emergency room nurses work in shifting schedules i.e. 1 week of shift from 6:00 AM to 2:00 PM or 2:00 PM to 10:00 PM and 10 PM to 6:00 AM shift.

Physical Activity

- Physical activity is defined as any body movement produced by skeletal muscles that result in energy expenditure. Energy expenditure can be measured in kilocalories. Physical activity in daily life can be categorized into occupational, sports, conditioning, household, or other activities.

Supportive Work Environment

- A supportive work environment offers numerous benefits for the employee and the employer. For the employee, it means going to work every day where both performance and well-being are accounted for. It means having managers who make time to help employees grow both personally and professionally. It fosters loyalty and working relationships in a healthy, pleasant environment (Hendricks, 2019)

Chapter II

Theoretical Background

Review of Related Literature

Compassion Fatigue

Over the past decade, compassion fatigue has been observed in health care providers but the definition of its characteristics and effects were inconsistent (Coetzee & Klopper, 2010). Compassion fatigue has been first used to refer to the experiences of nurses feeling burned out in the emergency room. The term used was compassion fatigue which at first reflected the adverse psychosocial consequences experienced by emergency department nurses. It was described in the nursing context as a large amount of stress caused by witnessing suffering, illness, and trauma in an ongoing day to day basis. Since 1970s, Figley (2002) has been studying the concept and initially called it a form of burnout or victimization and then later on adopted the term compassion fatigue as a more “friendly” term for this phenomenon. Figley (2002) described the act of being compassionate as bearing the suffering of others. This has implications such as an obsession with traumatized patients which may lead to compassion fatigue. Sorenson, Bolick, and Wright (2016) reviewed the current literature for understanding compassion fatigue in Health Care Providers (HCPs). The purpose of the review was to carefully give attention to provider role and practice area.

Compassion fatigue needs to be understood better to identify, prevent, and treat it before it could lead to problematic conditions of HCPs. Physical, emotional, and psychological symptoms contributed to the nurses' decision to leave their profession. In simplest form, Boyle (2011) cited in his study a definition of compassion fatigue as a state of psychic exhaustion -a severe malaise resulting from caring for patients experiencing varying aspects of pain such as physical, emotional and social.

As time passed, many studies were conducted but the definition of compassion is still unclear. According to the study of Mahdie et al. (2017), the word compassion fatigue is not a new concept but it is often overlooked as it is not well known and it has no clear definition. With the absence of a clear definition or the existence of confusing definitions, there has been a lack of awareness regarding the concept. In the end, compassion fatigue in nurses was defined as a "cumulative and progressive process of absorption of the patient's pain and suffering formed from the sympathetic and caring interactions with the patients and their families". Also, they emphasized that the consequences of compassion fatigue are so extensive that they threaten the existential integrity of the nurses in terms of their physical, emotional, intellectual, spiritual and organizational integrity. The risk of compassion fatigue is associated with factors such as devotion behaviors and commitment towards the patient, exposure to multiple stressors, organizational challenges, and lack of self-care. Concretely defining the concept is the first step to protect nurses against the consequences of compassion fatigue and to improve quality of care and life.

Research studies on compassion fatigue from 2010 up to the present have evolved. Boyle (2011) characterized compassion fatigue as the progressive state of

unease which evolves from compassion discomfort to compassion stress that leads to compassion fatigue. Cocker & Joss (2016) characterized compassion fatigue as experiencing exhaustion, anger, irritability, adopting negative coping behaviors including alcohol and drug abuse, reduced ability to feel sympathy and empathy, diminished sense of enjoyment or satisfaction with work, increase absenteeism, and an impaired ability to make decisions and care for patients. Mathias and Wentzel (2017) defined compassion as the backbone of professionals who truly care. It is when care providers empathize with the suffering or misfortune of others and understand the client's personal feelings or experience without judgement and prejudice. Therefore, providing quality of care and empathy should always be intertwined with the care provider thinking of how he or she would like to be treated in the same situation. Moreover, the researcher described the concept as a negative outcome of prolonged compassion fatigue. Compassion fatigue has been described as being preoccupied with or re-experiencing the patient's traumatic events which consequently reduce the care providers' aptitude or interest in bearing the suffering of other people. Exposure to such stressful situations, personal and professional ethical conflicts and dilemma, frequent contact with dying patients, and constant suffering are all in the nature of the nursing profession which can diminish emotional responsiveness.

If compassion is left unresolved, this often causes physical and emotional exhaustion and can significantly impair job performance (Sheppard, 2015). A better understanding of compassion fatigue is highly recommended to improve the overall well-being of health care practitioners and ultimately to enhance patient care and staff retention within the profession.

Burnout and Vicarious Trauma

Stamm (2010) proposed a diagram for professional quality of life wherein compassion fatigue has two elements: (1) burnout and (2) vicarious trauma. According to Bouchard (2016), compassion fatigue is a phenomenon commonly described as the combined negative impact of burnout and vicarious trauma. Compassion fatigue may either lead to burnout or vicarious trauma when left unresolved.

Maslach (2003) posited the theory of burnout where the primary interest is on emotions which cause occupational burnout. In early studies and research, burnout focused more on “caregiving” and in the relationship established with an individual receiving care. According to the theory, burnout is a mismatch between the person doing the job and the demands of the job. It is comprised of three dimensions such as emotional exhaustion, cynicism or depersonalization, and inefficacy. Among the three, emotional exhaustion is the most visible and noticeable dimension. Burnout also exhibits various symptoms such as emotional stress, moodiness, frustration, and agitation. These symptoms may lead to the inability to cope with high job demands, minimal job resources, and the emotional and physical aspects of the job (Ndawula, 2012).

Burnout is defined as a psychological syndrome that involves a prolonged response to chronic interpersonal stressors on the job (Leiter & Maslach, 2004). While like compassion fatigue, burnout has different physical and psychological components. Burnout is triggered by workplace stressors “such as manager unresponsiveness, lack of camaraderie and team work, staffing shortages, long working hours, intense workloads, conflicts with other nurses and healthcare providers, and time pressures” (Boyle, 2015). Adriaenssens, De Gucht, and Maes (2014), conducted a systematic

review of empirical quantitative studies on the determinants and prevalence of burnout in emergency nurses spanning 25 years. According to the study, “it is an important problem in health care professional and is associated with decrease occupational well-being and increase in absenteeism, turnover and illness”. Since emergency nurses are often faced with patient overcrowding, unpredictable situations, and prolonged exposure to a broad range of diseases, injuries, and traumatic events, they are found to be vulnerable to burnout. In the seventeen studies conducted, an average of twenty six percent (26%) of the emergency nurses suffered from burnout. The study explored the prevalence of burnout and identified its specific (individual and work related) determinants. Results showed that individual factors such as demographic variables, personality characteristics, and coping strategies were predictive variables of burnout. Furthermore, work related factors such as exposure to traumatic events, job characteristics, and organizational variables were found as determinant factors of burnout. Therefore, job demands, job control, social support, and exposure to traumatic events are burnout determinants together with several organizational variables. As a result of the study, the hospital management formulated a plan of action to prevent the turnover and burnout among emergency room nurses. In another study conducted to evaluate an active intervention if it can decrease job burnout and improve the performance of emergency nurses, three hospitals were randomly selected from eight comprehensive high-level hospitals in China. A total of 102 nurses participated in the study and was randomly divided into control and intervention groups. The intervention group was treated with comprehensive management while the control group was treated with ordinary management. Results of the study showed different levels and

symptoms of job burnout among emergency nurses. The data indicated that comprehensive management significantly decreased the emotional exhaustion and depersonalization of the nurses. Consequently, the findings suggested that active intervention with comprehensive management considerably reduced job burnout, contributed to relieving work-related stress, and promoted safety against potential mental health problems (Wei et al., 2017).

Studies have shown that secondary traumatic stress also known as vicarious trauma is the negative change that happens to health practitioners overtime as they witness other people's suffering and need. In addition, vicarious trauma is the process of change that happens because of caring for other people who have been hurt, and the subsequent feeling of commitment or responsibility to help them. Over time, this process can lead to changes in the psychological, physical, and spiritual well-being.

Rutledge and Dominguez-Gomez (2009) conducted a research using an exploratory comparative design with 67 emergency nurses from three general community hospitals in California. The purpose of the study was to investigate the prevalence of vicarious trauma in emergency nurses using survey instruments such as the demographic tool and the Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) survey. The results of the study showed that fifty four percent (54%) of nurses were most likely to have arousal symptoms/ irritability, followed by avoidance symptoms or avoidance of patients at fifty two percent (52%), and intrusion symptoms or intrusive thoughts about patients scored at forty six percent (46%). Majority of the nurses or eighty five percent (85%) reported at least one symptom in the past week. The results indicate that high prevalence of STS will have negative effects among a large population of emergency

room nurses. These symptoms may contribute to emotional exhaustion and job separation of nurses which will subsequently lead to job dissatisfaction or burnout. Emergency department nurses are required to deal with emotional trauma on a daily basis which may result to different kinds of symptoms of STS (Duffy, Avalos, & Dowling, 2015). STS is a consequence of the stress experienced when helping a person who is traumatized or is suffering. One hundred seventeen nurses in three emergency departments in the Western region of Ireland were invited to complete the Secondary Traumatic Stress Scale or STSS. Eighty two percent (82%) reported significant findings where the highest proportion of STS existed in the staff nurse group. Ninety percent (90%) response rate was achieved when the study was conducted. Statistical significance showed variables such as career changes were considered by the respondents while alcohol was found to be helpful in alleviating work-related stress. The study's findings suggest the need to examine current crisis management interventions and introduce new systems to support nurses in emergency departments.

The effect of vicarious trauma emanates from a job that is focused on helping others while being exposed to traumatic experiences. Learning about and awareness of vicarious trauma is important to make sure that this will not lead to burnout or compassion fatigue and unintentionally hurt oneself or others. To do this, the first step is to understand more about vicarious trauma.

The Triggering Factors

Working as a professional health care provider is one example of an occupation with a higher risk of acquiring compassion fatigue because they have close interpersonal contact with the patient who suffers. As defined by Stamm (2012), helpers can be anyone as long as there is

an interaction with another person with the objective of offering assistance. Nurses are at risk of becoming emotionally dulled by their caring work. They are at risk of developing compassion fatigue especially when they get to a point wherein they learn to turn off their emotions towards their patients (Young, Cicchillo, & Bressier, 2011). According to Watson (2010), the core of the nursing role is empathic caring or empathic response. However, the cost of providing this empathic nursing care can contribute and lead to compassion fatigue. Lombardo et.al (2011) defined empathy as the ability to understand patient's feelings, understand the patient's situation from their perspective, and the ability to communicate understanding to the patient. Individuals who present high levels of empathy or empathic response to patient's pain, suffering, or traumatic experiences are more vulnerable to triggering compassion fatigue (Adams et.al., 2006). The three key dimensions of this stress response are overwhelming exhaustion, feelings of cynicism and detachment from the job, and sense of ineffectiveness and lack of accomplishment (Maslach, 2003). Moreover, STS or vicarious trauma is about work-related, secondary exposure to people who have experienced extreme, traumatic, and stressful events (Stamm, 2010) such as patients and colleagues. Joinson (2015) noted that "when the people around you are tense, impatient, and hurried, you may be swept into the same reactions. Nurses who are tired, indifferent, or cynical can sap your own energy and enthusiasm." Jenkins & Warren (2012) identified consequences resulting to compassion fatigue which include loss of empathy, increase loss of work days due to physical constraints, weight gain or weight loss, accident proneness, and emotional breakdown. Moreover, the development of compassion fatigue can be related to individual factors associated with personality, work responsibilities, and processes of engaging with others, as well as macro-level environmental and cultural factors (Bouchard, 2016). These are the factors that can trigger and lead to compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. According to Leiter & Maslach (2004), there are six factors that may affect work-life balance: workload, control, rewards, community, fairness, and values. These factors influence nurses' decision to leave his or her profession.

Environment of Emergency Room Department

The emergency department plays a vital key role in injured and severely ill patients. It serves as a front line of care and is often the only accessible source of care for uninsured patients or those who otherwise lack access to medical services (Schumacher Group, 2010). In fact, the World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the importance of the state or community's ability to deliver quality emergency care, recognizing the growing implications for public health given the increasing burden of medical, surgical, and traumatic emergency conditions (Nyhus & Kamara, 2017). In a study conducted in Iran, Hossein et al. (2012) stated that "No hospital can be considered as an ideal treatment center without an active and fully functional emergency room". This unit, if properly used, will save many people. Also, hectic environment and a variety of clinical responsibilities are mostly common in ED (Jeanmonod et al., 2011). In addition, ED is often the "gateway" to the health system and provision of immediate attendance. With an atmosphere of unpredictability and uncertainty, the health care professionals who work in this environment require knowledge, speed of reasoning, and promptness in decision-making (Garcia, 2010). Because of the high workload, such demands overlap and overload in the ED services, compromising the quality of care given to the patients (Rossetti, 2013). On the other hand, a study conducted in Australia about emergency nurse practitioners resulted to changes in their work and the nurses are now well established and are members of a well-respected healthcare team. Emergency room nurses and the department offer great flexibility and adaptation to the changing needs of health service delivery within the healthcare team (Jennings et al., 2016). Similarly, Crilly, Greenslade, and Fisher (2017) characterized the emergency department as having high workload and competing demands. The study they conducted aimed to know the perception of ED nurses on their work environment. The research was a cross-sectional pilot study involving nurses working in one ED in Queensland, Australia. The respondents of the study were surveyed using the Working

Environment Score or WES-10 which consists of four subscales: self-realization, workload, conflict and nervousness. It is used to measure stress and staff morale. The study identified that ED nurses' satisfaction with their working environment was relatively high and perception of workload was higher. The highlight of the study included the following findings: repeated exposure to stressors can result in burnout and staff attrition, workload impacted most of the respondents in their working environment, and understanding work environment can inform targeted improvement strategies.

Compassion Fatigue among Emergency Nurses

Nurses working in ED have a higher risk of developing compassion fatigue. They consistently witness human suffering, pain, traumatic injuries, violence, and death that triggers compassion fatigue's development. The intense nature of their working environment and the traumatic events they witnessed or experienced become the source of compassion fatigue (Petleski, 2013). The results showed nearly eighty six percent (86%) moderate to high levels of compassion fatigue compared with other special areas (Hooper, Craig, & Janvrin, 2010). Bassmayor, (2013) concluded that in most Metro Manila based nurses, they employ problem-focused coping styles in dealing with the phenomenon of compassion fatigue. In addition, a study conducted by Casi (2016) compared the prevalence of compassion fatigue among 147 nurses, residents, and fellows who worked in the pediatric department of Philippine General Hospital. The study's results noted the highest prevalence of compassion fatigue at thirty nine percent (39%) among residents and proportion among fellows and nurses at eighteen percent (18%). While the study was used as a guideline, it did not solely focus on nurses or ED nurses. There is no updated study which focused on Filipino nurses working in the emergency room department and their awareness of compassion fatigue. In addition, there are limited local resources and information available about the subject. There is an existing gap in literature about compassion fatigue, specifically among Filipino ED nurses.

Synthesis of Related Literature

A literature review was conducted to explore the current available research related to compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout, triggers affecting compassion fatigue, environment of the emergency room, and compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout among emergency nurses. Cumulative Index to Nursing Allied Health Literature, Science Direct and ProQuest were used to search for studies using the keywords: compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, burnout, emergency room department, and emergency room nurses. The researcher excluded research studies published before 2010.

Theoretical Framework

Complex Relationships

Figure 1. Application of Beth Hudnall Stamm Complex Relationships Theoretical Path Analysis (Stamm, 2009).

The framework used to guide this research was Stamm’s Professional Quality of Life. It includes the elements of Professional Quality of Life that illustrate compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue (Stamm, 2012). The Professional Quality of Life Scale, also known as ProQOL, is the most commonly used tool to measure compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue. It was originally known as Compassion Fatigue Self-test developed by Charles Figley. In the 1990s, Figley and Stamm (1995) renamed the test Professional Quality of Life Scale. This tool was used to measure compassion fatigue among nurses working in specialized areas such as the emergency room.

ProQOL has a complex concept because of its three domains, namely, work environment which corresponds to organizational and task-wise, the client environment or the individual's personal characteristics, and the personal environment, which corresponds to the care provider's exposure to primary and secondary trauma in their work. Moreover, the three domains will eventually lead to either compassion satisfaction which is the positive aspect of helping others or compassion fatigue which is the opposite and shows the negative aspect of helping others. According to Stamm (2012), compassion satisfaction is the pleasure derived from being able to do well at work while compassion fatigue is defined by positive and negative aspects. The positive aspect is also considered as compassion satisfaction and the negative is compassion fatigue. An example of situation which may lead to both compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue is a person working in a poor work environment with limited resources may experience compassion fatigue because of his or her circumstance. However, if he or she can still help others despite the limited resources and poor working environment provided, compassion satisfaction can be gained.

In addition, compassion fatigue branches out into two parts. The first part includes exhaustion, frustration, anger, and depression caused by the work environment known as burnout. The second part involves traumatic stress secondary to work-related trauma known as vicarious trauma. These two variables may result in experiencing compassion fatigue overtime. Hence, the ProQOL tool is not a means to diagnose the respondents but to raise awareness and issues to be addressed. Results from the ProQOL test can be used as a guide for an individual and the organization. The results can also be used as baseline for the administration to assess the quality of care.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma and Burnout among nurses working in emergency room department.

The conceptual framework shown in Figure 2 illustrates four variables that lead to compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. These variables influence and change the effect of dependent variables. There are four sub-specifications under the independent variables. These are work environment, client environment, personal environment and demographic data.

The work environment is described as the surrounding condition in which an employee function. This can refer to physical conditions such as the resources used by nurses to provide quality of care such as computers, beds, cardiac monitors, blood pressure monitors, pulse oximeters, oxygen tanks and so on. On the other hand, social interactions refer to involvements in the workplace such as with peers, colleagues, subordinates, and managers. According to the American Nurses Association (ANA)

(2018), the work environment plays a big role in providing quality of care. The atmosphere of the facilities, the safety of the patient, and the health care provider's satisfaction are all part of the work environment. Another part of the work environment is the staffing linked to patients' outcome, length of stay, and chance of death. The ANA principles and guidelines for workplace safety cover aspects such as culture, healthy nursing working hours, working when fatigued, work release during disaster, and sexual harassment.

The client environment is encountered by nurses in their daily duty and is referred to as the "patients". The patients' satisfaction towards the care rendered by the nurses, their behavior, the level of toxicity, and noise are also parts of the client environment. This environment also includes patients encountered in the emergency room department such as those on a vehicular accident, those pronounced dead on arrival, and even those with a cardiology case and so on.

The personal environment is within oneself. The prerequisites of the personal environment are health and safety. Personal environment examples are personal refuge and a place to escape stress. According to Kieft de Brouwer et al. (2014), essential elements to improve patient's experience of quality nursing care are clinically competent nurses, collaborative working relationships, autonomous nursing practice, adequate staffing, managerial support, and patient-centered culture. Therefore, incorporating these elements will result in more positive experiences.

The independent variables for this study were the nurses working in the emergency room department. The independent variable stands alone and cannot be changed. This variable is constant and manipulated to determine the value of the

dependent variable. The researcher included the following information of emergency room department nurses during the data gathering: demographic data such as age, gender, and relationship status, physical activities, hospital sector, shift work, working hours per shift including the overtime work per hour, and the length of experience.

Lastly, the dependent variables of the study were compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. Dependent variables are the outcomes being studied. From the word itself “depend”, the dependent variables are variables that change depending on the factors that may affect it.

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: Nurses working in the emergency room department are not significantly aware of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

Ha1: Nurses working in the emergency room department are significantly aware of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between demographic data such as age, gender, relationship status and compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout

Ha1: There is a significant relationship between demographic data such as age, gender, relationship status and compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

Chapter III

Research Methodology

This chapter covers the research design, research instrument and tools, description of the study setting, research variables, sampling scheme, sample size, method and procedure of data collection, and statistical treatment that the researcher used.

Research Design

This research study used an exploratory correlational design to explore and determine the level of awareness about compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among nurses working in the emergency department of selected tertiary hospitals. This study design was utilized in order to determine the relationship with other possible variables such as demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment. The research mainly used exploratory surveys and questionnaires such as the Professional Quality of Life Scale Version 5 (ProQOL) by Stamm (2012) as a guideline. The ProQOL has 30 items which assessed how often the respondents have had certain feelings related to their work as a health care provider. Through the use of this validated instrument tool, awareness among nurses working in the emergency room department about compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout was measured and intervention was applied to increase the rate of compassion satisfaction rather than compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

Research Instrument and Tools

The research questionnaire contained two sections. The first section was composed of demographic, personal, work-life, thoughts about compassion fatigue,

vicarious trauma and burnout questions and the second section included the ProQOL Version 5 (Stamm, 2012).

The primary objective of the study was to describe the level of awareness and determine the level of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout of emergency room nurses. Furthermore, the researcher wanted to identify if there was a significant relationship between compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout with the following variables: demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment. As suggested by Figley's Compassion Stress Fatigue Model (2002), the questions were aimed to gather data related to the nurse's level of exposure and other potential triggers for compassion fatigue. Examples of exposure questions include length of years in nursing, hours worked for a week and the amount of overtime shifts, and the number of handled patient per shift, all of which are possible factors that can trigger the risk of experiencing compassion fatigue. In addition, work-life questions such as shiftwork, extra shiftwork, attitude towards work, supportive work environment, and work-life balance including exercise or leisure activities were included in the questionnaire. Furthermore, demographic questions such as age, gender, relationship status, and number of children were also included.

The ProQOL Version 5 is composed of 30 items pertaining to work related thoughts, feelings, and behaviors rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). It has three subscales with ten questions each covering compassion satisfaction, burnout, and secondary trauma stress also known as vicarious trauma. ProQOL Version 5 was primarily used in this research study for several reasons. The first and main reason of using this instrument as noted by Stamm (2012) was that "it is

the most commonly used measure of the positive and negative effects of working with people who have experienced extremely stressful events”. Second, the instrument was made accessible by the author to anyone, free of charge. The author of ProQOL also included translations of the instrument to various languages and the present study used the Filipino language or Tagalog translation of the questionnaire to avoid misunderstanding and miscommunication with the respondents. Lastly, ProQOL was meant to be used and was developed to help professionals such as those in the nursing profession. At the end of the ProQOL scale, the researcher provided another questionnaire to get the respondents’ thoughts and opinions on compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout which was answerable by a yes or no.

Research Setting

The study was conducted within the province of Laguna, Philippines. Only tertiary hospitals were included in the study. The Department of Health (DOH) (2015) listed ten (10) tertiary hospitals accredited within the province of Laguna. Due to the difficulty of leveling the hospitals, the researcher used the list of tertiary hospitals provided by DOH (2015) and then randomly selected the hospitals within the area. All ten (10) hospitals chosen approved and consented to participate in the study. Random sampling was used to achieve the target sample size of one hundred thirty three (133) emergency room nurse respondents. Ethical considerations for the study included the anonymization of the hospital as well as the respondents and the use of correspondent code numbers to protect their privacy.

Research Variable

Dependent variables used in the study were compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout while the independent variables were emergency room department nurses, work

environment, client environment, and personal environment. Furthermore, independent variables included nurses who work in both public and private hospital, extra shift worked, hours worked per shift, years of experience as an emergency room nurse, and years of experience as a nurse. In addition to the independent variables are the demographic data such as gender, age, marital status, number of children, and work environment such as the positive attitude and support of colleagues. Henceforward, variables such as the demographic data, work environment, client environment and personal environment were included and determined through the ProQOL Version 5 (Stamm, 2012).

Sampling Scheme

Respondents of the study included nurses who worked in the emergency room department of selected tertiary hospitals within Laguna. Furthermore, the study's inclusion criteria were:

- 1.) Nurses assigned in the emergency department regardless if they were classified as trainee, probationary, or regular staff of the hospital
- 2.) Nurses from both the public and private hospital sector
- 3.) Nurses aged 20 to 50 years old
- 4.) Nurses with six months and beyond experience in the profession
- 5.) Nurses with six months and beyond experience in the emergency room
- 6.) Nurses from all genders
- 7.) Nurses with and without children.

The exclusion criteria of the study were:

- 1.) Nurses who were not currently working in the emergency room department (i.e. operating room, intensive-care unit, dialysis nurse and etc.)
- 2.) Other health care providers such as doctors, nursing aids, midwife and etc.

3.) Non-tertiary hospitals according to the Department of Health (2015) list.

Ethical considerations of the study included nurses who voluntarily signed the consent form. The nurses were also informed that they could self-exclude if they did not wish to partake in the study.

Sample Size

Statistical power and sample size for the study were determined using the G*Power version 3.1.9.2. For the analysis of data, the study used the family of t-tests, the point of Biserial model for the statistical test of correlation, and the type of power analysis of A priori by computing the required sample size, α , power, and effect size. Input parameters used were two-tailed, an effect size of $[p] = 0.3$, probability of error at $\alpha = 0.05$, power ($1 - \beta$ probability of error) = 0.95 and allocation ration of $N2/N1 = 1$. The sample size was calculated to be at one hundred eleven (111). Additional twenty percent (20%) was added to address possible attrition. It was determined that the study needed a total of one hundred thirty-three (133) emergency room nurse respondents.

Method and procedure of Data Collection

The following steps were employed in conducting the research study. Approval of the research by the Ethical Review Board was likewise obtained.

Phase 1 - *Planning Phase*. Courtesy call and asking permission from hospital administrators were conducted. The chief nurse in each hospital was consulted during the planning phase. Once consent for the study was provided and approved by the

administrator, the chief nurses or the head unit/supervisor of the emergency room department were advised about the study and the data collection process.

Phase 2 - *Informed Consent*. Respondents who qualified based on the study's inclusion criteria and were willing to participate were provided a written consent form (Appendix D). The consent form was secured afterwards before the data collection started.

Phase 3 - *Dissemination of Demographic, Personal and Work- Life Questionnaire and ProQOL Questionnaire*. Distribution of questionnaire was through the respondents' email address/ Facebook messenger and/or through paper distribution depending on their preference. The respondents who asked for the questionnaires to be sent through their email addresses were assigned a research assistant to guide them in answering the entire questionnaire and to secure the validity of the answer. On the other hand, those who chose Facebook messenger to access the questionnaire were contacted through video call/face time for guidance. The researcher used a new Facebook messenger account named MANRKPB to provide anonymity. Lastly, designated locked drawers were provided to secure the answer sheets of the respondents who chose to answer the questionnaire through paper distribution. Approximately fifteen minutes of the respondents' time was consumed to completely answer the questionnaire. After which, all answers were deleted and destroyed once data was tabulated. Consequently, as the respondents' time was consumed, a small token of appreciation such as a free meal was provided. One hundred pesos (Php 100.00) budget was allocated for each

respondent. During the staff meeting, access to the emergency room department was requested to discuss the research study with potential respondents.

The findings of the study can serve as baseline data for developing a program to improve not only emergency room nurses but also other health care providers to balance their work/life condition. The study can also contribute to nurses' advancement of practice and a copy of the results will be shared to the respondent's key stakeholder, upon their request, to serve as references. The researcher allocated one to two days for each hospital to get through every shift of the respondents and guide them if there were queries. As there was an identifiable risk for the researcher's safety in travelling since there were hospitals involved in the study that required physical presence, a car insurance worth eleven thousand five hundred pesos (Php 11,500.00) was applied for last November 29, 2018 until November 29, 2019 through the Oriental Assurance Corporation. Allocated travel insurance worth four hundred fifty thousand pesos (P450,000) for the driver was likewise applied for. Both the research assistant and data collectors were compensated according to their regular per hour rate at work. Questionnaire distribution was conducted for the whole month of January 2019 and collection of answered questionnaire was done until the last day of the month. The questionnaires that were not submitted after the due date were considered null and void for the study.

Phase 4 - *Collecting Data*. All collected data were secured to maintain privacy and confidentiality. A respondent may only view his or her personal results upon his or her

request while a copy of the entire research study results can be made available to participating institutions upon their request.

Phase 5 – *Intervention*. After data collection and analysis, intervention and/or recommendations were provided.

Pre-testing of Tools/Pilot Study

Pre-testing and pilot study are important steps to test the validity of the survey questionnaire before data collection. These can help identify questions that can be misunderstood or questions that might lead to biased answers. The questionnaire used for this study was pre-tested in a different tertiary hospital in Laguna following the same inclusion and exclusion criteria. The same method and procedure for data collection was used during the pre-testing. The respondents of the pre-test were asked to complete the survey while thinking out loud and the researcher observed how the respondents completed the survey. Suggestions and recommendations arising from the pre-test were taken into consideration.

Ethical Consideration

Throughout the entire research process, careful attention was given to ethical considerations. The research was guided and supervised by an assigned Faculty-in-Charge (FIC). Suggestions and recommendations provided by the FIC were taken into consideration and applied by the researcher.

Voluntary participation of the respondents in the research was important. Respondents were given the free will and the right to withdraw from the study at any stage if they wish to do so. Respondents were provided with a written consent form and this consent form was secured before the data collection commenced. The researcher discussed the principles and objectives of the research to the respondents. Sufficient information was likewise provided and the respondents were assured that they have the freedom to decide whether or not they wish to partake in the study without any pressure or coercion. The use of offensive, discriminatory, and unacceptable language was omitted and avoided in the formulation of the questionnaire. However, given the nature of the variables being measured, some questions could trigger negative emotions, feelings, or bad memories. Furthermore, all information and answers of the respondents were kept confidential. Privacy and anonymity of the answers were strictly implemented by securing the answer sheets in a box provided. Results of the study may be given and may be distributed individually upon request.

Plan for Data Analysis and Interpretation

G*Power version 3.1.9.2 was used to analyze the data with all raw data input. This program was used to perform all statistical analyses. Data was plotted for normality before analyses were conducted. The demographic information of the respondents (age, gender, relationship status, years of experience, etc.) was analyzed and

summarized using descriptive analysis. Chi-square correlation was used to evaluate the strength of each variable's relationship with a significance level of 0.5.

For the analysis of the ProQOL questionnaire, the study followed the instructions in the ProQOL manual (Stamm, 2012, p.16) where raw scores on each of the three subscales were converted to standardized t-scores. The manual provided cut scores for each subscale to enable the researcher to assess the risk level by determining the percentage of respondents that fall below the 25th percentile or above the 75th percentile. Furthermore, in order to assess for differences on the ProQOL subscales across the independent groups, analyses of variance frequency, chi-square, mean, and standard deviation were performed. Significance level of p value <0.5 was set to identify a significant relationship among the variables in the study.

Figure 3 summarizes the method and procedure of data collection.

Figure 3. Flow Diagram of Study

Chapter IV

Results, Analysis, and Interpretation

In this chapter, results of the study will be discussed and presented together with the analysis and interpretation. Tables are presented according to the objectives of the

study. The respondents' level of awareness and the risk of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout will be discussed. In addition, correlation among the demographic data, personal, work-life, and the respondents' thoughts about compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout will also be presented.

Table 1. Level of awareness of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout among emergency room nurses ($n = 129$).

VARIABLES	(f)	(%)
Compassion Fatigue		
Yes	53	41.1%
No	64	49.6%
Not Sure	12	9.3%
Vicarious Trauma		
Yes	37	28.7%
No	64	49.6%
Not Sure	28	9.3%
Burnout		
Yes	120	93%
No	3	2.3%
Not Sure	6	4.7%

Table 1. Continued...

VARIABLES	(f)	(%)
Program or assistance in dealing with Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma and Burnout		
Yes	10	7.8%

No	77	59.7%
Not Sure	42	32.6%
How important an issue do you feel Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma and Burnout in workplace		
Very Important	101	78.3%
Somewhat Important	24	18.6%
Not Important	1	0.8%
Not Sure	3	2.3%

Table 1 describes the respondents' level of awareness about compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. The respondents were asked about their thoughts on compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout and they were given the options of yes, no, and not sure. In compassion fatigue, majority of the respondents or 64 individuals (49.6%) have not heard of the term. On the other hand, 53 respondents (41.1%) answered yes and were familiar with the term while 12 respondents (9.3%) were not sure. In vicarious trauma, majority of the respondents or 64 individuals (49.6%) were not familiar with the term while there were 37 (28.7%) respondents familiar with it and 28 (21.7%) answered that they were not sure about the term. In burnout, majority of the respondents or 120 individuals (93%) were familiar with the term while only three respondents (2.3%) have not heard of burnout and six (4.7%) were not sure of it.

The respondents were also asked if their workplace offers any program or assistance in dealing with compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout and how important an issue they feel these are in their workplace. Table 1 shows that majority or

77 individuals (59.7%) agreed that there were no programs or assistance in dealing with compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout provided. Ten (7.8%) answered yes to having the said programs and assistance in their institutions while 42 respondents (32.6%) were not sure of its existence. Hence, the ten respondents who answered yes likewise answered the follow up question on specifying the programs offered. Furthermore, 101 respondents (78.3%) felt that the issue is very important in their workplace while 24 (18.6%) answered that the issue is somewhat important, three respondents (2.3%) were not sure, and only one person (0.8%) answered that the issue is not important.

Table 1 also shows that the respondents from both public and private institutions were not aware of compassion fatigue and vicarious trauma. Although there were some individuals who were somewhat familiar about the terms, more than 50% were still unfamiliar with these. On the other hand, nurses in the emergency room were more aware of the term burnout. 93% were familiar with burnout as the term was commonly tackled or used in health care. Programs or assistance regarding this matter were not offered by the hospital management or nursing service department. The results also show that for nurses, the three concepts were important issues to know and be aware of to prevent the risk of acquiring either of the three.

Based on the results, the nurses value the importance of knowing the issue which is the first step to increasing awareness and lessening the risk of acquiring compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. As cited by Hall (2017), it's about time that we applied our understanding of this potentially destructive term to our own profession. Thus, the current work environment appears to foster a healthy balance and

work environment interventions can be directed to increase levels of compassion satisfaction rather than prevent compassion fatigue.

Table 2. Demographic, Personal and Work- Life Profile of the Respondents (*n* = 129).

VARIABLES	(f)	(%)
Hospital Sector		
Public	42	32.6%
Private	87	67.4%
Age		
20 – 29	71	55.0%
30 – 39	40	31.0%
40 – 49	16	12.4%
Above 50	2	1.6%
Gender		
Female	77	59.7%
Male	52	40.3%

Table 2. Continued...

VARIABLES	(f)	(%)
Years of Experience in the emergency room		
0 – 5years	91	70.5%

6 – 10years	21	16.3%
11 – 15years	12	9.3%
15years or more	5	3.9%
Years of Experience as a Nurse		
0 – 5years	55	42.6%
6 – 10years	41	31.8%
11 – 15years	19	14.7%
15 years or more	14	10.9%
Relationship Status		
Single	79	61.2%
Married or Common Law	50	38.8%
Separated, Divorced or Widowed	0	0
Parent		
Yes	53	41.1%
No	76	58.9%

Table 2. Continued...

VARIABLES	(f)	(%)
Hours worked per week		
16 or less	31	24.0%

17 – 31	1	0.8%
32 or more	97	75.2%
Shift work		
Yes	113	87.6%
No	16	12.4%
Extra shift work		
More than once per month	72	55.8%
Once every 1 -3 months	7	5.4%
Rarely	40	31.0%
Never	10	7.8%
Physical Activity		
Frequently (at least 3days per week)	26	20.2%
Often (at least 3days per month)	39	30.2%
Rarely	62	48.1%
Never	2	1.6%

Table 2. Continued...

VARIABLES	(f)	(%)
Supportive work environment		
Strongly Agree	31	24.0%

Agree	65	50.4%
Neutral	28	21.7%
Disagree	5	3.9%
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Positive attitude towards work		
Strongly Agree	33	25.6%
Agree	76	58.9%
Neutral	20	15.5%
Disagree	0	0
Strongly Disagree	0	0

Table 2 describes the demographic, personal, and work-life profile of the respondents. Results show that 42 respondents (32.6%) were from public hospitals and 87 respondents (67.4%) came from private hospitals. In terms of the age group, 71 respondents (55%) were aged 20 – 29 years old, 40 respondents (31%) were aged 30 – 39 years old, 16 (12.4%) were aged 40 – 49 years old, and only two individuals (1.6%) were above 50 years of age. In terms of gender, Table 2 shows that there were 77 female respondents (59.7%) and 52 male respondents (40.3%). In terms of relationship status, choices provided in the questionnaire were single, married or common law, separated, divorced or widowed. There were no separated, divorced or widowed respondents in the study. 79 respondents (61.2%) were single and 50 (38.8%) was married or in a common law relationship. Besides relationship status, the study also

asked if the respondents are with a child or not. 53 respondents (41.1%) reported having a child while 76 (58.9%) does not.

Summarizing the results in Table 2, majority of the respondents were female who worked in private tertiary hospitals in the province of Laguna and were within the age group of 20-29 years old. More than half of the nurse respondents were single, and majority were childless. Generally, the results of the study showed that majority of the nurse respondents working for tertiary hospitals in Laguna were from private institutions as opposed to government hospitals. Similar to these findings, Lavado's (2011) study on the "Profile of Private Hospitals in the Philippines" showed that majority of the hospitals in the country are privately owned and most of these hospitals are operating as profit institutions. According to the study, Level 1 and 2 hospitals are well distributed compared with Level 3 and 4 hospitals. Hospital Level 3 and 4 are mostly located in urbanized areas and inpatient care has a higher case in these private hospitals. CALABARZON has one of the highest numbers of private hospitals in the Philippines. This can be attributed to the situation of the nurses in rural areas who struggle with their salaries, heavy workload, lack of opportunities for professional growth, and poor work environment (Labrague, 2018). Therefore, nurses prefer working in urban areas where most hospitals have considerably competitive compensation. The adverse effect of these influence the work performance, work satisfaction, work commitment, and ultimately increase the nurses' intention to leave their jobs based on the study.

Millennial nurses born between 1980 and 2000 will make up almost 50% of the nation's workforce by 2020 (Kosterlitz, 2017). This population captures the crown from the baby boomer generation and generation X. Based on the results of Table 2, more

than half of the respondents were 20-29 years of age. This group grew up in the digital era, social media, and pervasive online presence. They can adapt easily to change, learn and operate new systems, and perform well using computer-based equipment compared to those from the generation X and baby boomers. Turnover rate is also higher unlike with the generation X and baby boomers as nurses nowadays are quick to transfer to a new company if they are unhappy with the leadership, pay, or career growth opportunities.

Moreover, for the question on how long have the nurses worked in the emergency room, results showed that majority or 91 respondents (70.5%) have been working for 0 – 5 years, 21 respondents (16.3%) have been working for 6 -10 years, 12 respondents (9.3%) have been working for 11 – 15 years, and lastly five respondents (3.9%) have been working in the emergency room for 15 years or more. In terms of their length of career as a nurse, 55 respondents (42.6%) have been nurses for 0 -5 years, 41 respondents (31.8%) have been nurses for 6 – 10 years, 19 respondents (14.7%) have been nurses for 11 – 15 years, and 14 respondents (10.9%) have been nurses for 15 years or more. Their number of hours worked per week showed that majority or 97 respondents (75.2%) worked 32 hours or more while 31 respondents (24%) worked 16 hours or less and only one (0.8%) worked for 17 – 31 hours. Furthermore, the nurses' shift work was described, and results showed that 113 respondents (87.6%) answered that they do shift work while 16 respondents (12.4%) do not. For extra shift work, 72 respondents (55.8%) rendered overtime more than once per month while seven respondents (5.4%) worked overtime once every 1 – 3 months. 40 respondents (31%) rarely do extra shift work and ten respondents (7.8%) never rendered this extra work. In

terms of engaging in any physical activity, majority or 62 (48.1%) reported that they rarely participate in physical activities while 26 respondents (20.2%) reported that they do these activities frequently or at least three days per week. 39 respondents (30.2%) do physical activities often or at least three days per month and only two respondents (1.6%) do not engage in any forms of physical activity.

To summarize the key findings in Table 2, 70% of nurses in the study have been working in the emergency room department for 0-5 years while majority have been in the nursing profession for only 0-5 years also. Majority of the nurse respondents reported that they work 32 hours or more within a week and render shift work. Moreover, despite the respondents' rendered hours of service and extra shift hours, their physical engagement outside of work was found to be non-existent.

House Bill no. 2548 known as An Act Providing for a Comprehensive Nursing Law towards Safe and Quality Health Care System, re-appealing for this purpose, Republic Act 9173 otherwise known as the Philippine Nursing Act 2002 explained that the country's health situation remains poor due to chronic poverty while there are plenty of nursing professionals in the clinical settings. Inadequate salaries and benefits, lack of jobs and security of tenure, and inhumane working conditions push many nurses to seek better opportunities abroad. In the Philippines, nurse-patient ratio as of 2016 was 1:40-80 while the ideal ratio believed to achieve quality care is at 1:4. Training program and contractualization are still rampant while the former President Benigno Aquino III vetoed the proposed entry salary grade for nurses which was salary grade 15. The house representative acknowledged that the government failed to ensure adequate pay and benefits for nurses. Moreover, in the late 2018 and early 2019, hospitals have been

experiencing a crisis brought by the scarcity of nurses. The Philippines is considered as the world's largest nurse exporter with nearly ninety percent (90%) of Filipino nurses working overseas. Factors affecting Filipino nurses' decision to migrate are low income, lack of benefits, lack of opportunities and professional growth, high patient-nurse ratios, and poor enforcement of nursing law (Castro-Palaganas, 2017). Despite this, hospitals still continue to build new health care institutions which force the ratio of nurses to patients to compensate.

The study also asked about the respondents' environment and positive attitude towards work through their agreement and disagreement to the following statements: "The department I work on is a supportive work environment." and "My colleagues demonstrate a positive attitude towards the work they do."

Based on the respondents' answer about having a supportive working environment, majority or 65 nurses (50.4%) agreed that they have a supportive working environment in the emergency room department. 31 nurses (24%) reported that they strongly agree that they are in a supportive working environment while 28 (21.7%) were neutral and five (3.9%) disagreed to having a supportive work setting. None of the respondents strongly disagreed to the statement. On the other hand, 76 respondents (58.9%) agreed that they have a positive attitude towards their work while 33 respondents (25.6%) strongly agreed to the statement. 20 respondents (15.5%) have a neutral disposition to the statement but none of respondents expressed their disagreement.

A key player in preventing the risk of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout is the policymakers who have a major role in providing good work environment for health professionals. Exploring and creating attractive, supportive, positive work environments are necessary for the leaders and managers to achieve. The objectives are to create a work environment that attracts individuals into the health profession, encourage them to remain in the health workforce, and enable health workers to perform effectively (Wiskow, 2010). In another study, managers can proactively create work environments that provide opportunities for connection and support among staff by establishing a culture of recognition. Trainings allow professional caregivers to reconnect with their personal mission and then relate it to the values and mission of the organization (Potter, 2013). Based on existing literature on compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout and the results of the present research, nurses from the emergency room departments of selected tertiary hospitals in Laguna have good working environment and colleagues with supportive work attitude.

Table 3. Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma, Burnout (*n* = 129).

INDIVIDUAL ITEMS	M	SD
I get satisfaction from being able to help people	4.18	0.592
I feel invigorated after working with those I help	3.40	0.931
I like my work as a nurse	3.73	0.846
I am pleased with how I am able to keep up with helping techniques and protocols	3.67	0.772
My work makes me feel satisfied	3.67	0.722

I have happy thoughts and feelings about those I help and how I could help them	3.83	0.719
I believe I can make a difference through my work	3.74	0.755
I am proud of what I can do to help	4.12	0.746
I have thoughts that I am a “success” as a nurse	3.59	0.816
INDIVIDUAL ITEMS	M	SD
I am happy that I chose to do this work	3.92	0.714
Mean	3.784	0.4592
Total Compassion Fatigue	37.84	4.592
I am happy	2.16	0.694
I feel connected to others	2.33	0.753
I am not as productive at work because I am losing sleep over traumatic experiences of a person I help	2.05	0.784
I feel trapped by my job as a nurse	2.58	0.863
I have beliefs that sustain me	2.40	0.776
I am the person I always wanted to be	2.18	0.795
I feel worn out because of my work as a nurse	3.16	0.824
I feel overwhelmed because my case work load seems endless	3.16	0.798
I feel “bogged down” by the system	2.92	0.844
I am a very caring person	1.89	0.628

Mean	2.484	0.3521
Total Burnout	24.84	3.521
I am preoccupied with more than one person I help	3.26	0.796
I jump or am startled by unexpected sounds	2.36	0.901
I find it difficult to separate my personal life from my life as a nurse	2.47	0.985
INDIVIDUAL ITEMS	M	SD
I think that I might have been affected by the traumatic stress of those I help	2.16	0.788
Because of my helping, I have felt “on edge” about various things	2.88	0.915
I feel depressed because of the traumatic experiences of the people I help	2.27	0.942
I feel as though I am experiencing the trauma of someone I have helped	2.40	1.003
I avoid certain activities or situations because they remind me of frightening experiences	2.22	0.921
As a result of my helping, I have intrusive, frightening thoughts	2.05	0.975
I can't recall important parts of my work with trauma victims.	2.57	0.808
Mean	2.466	0.5598
Total Vicarious Trauma	24.66	5.598

A total of 129 respondents answered the 30-item questionnaire to know if there was existing compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among the respondents. The 30 questions are divided into three subscales with question number 3, 6, 12, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 27, and 30 for compassion satisfaction subscale. Vicarious trauma is determined by question number 2, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 14, 23, 25, and 28. Lastly, burnout is described by question number 1, 4, 8, 10, 15, 17, 19, 21, 26, and 29. Answers for item number 1, 4, 15, 17, and 29 were reversed according to the instrument's instruction. These items were reversed during analysis because scientifically, the measure works better when the questions are asked in a positive way, but its negative statement can inform the study more (Stamm, 2012). To determine the level of the following subscales: compassion satisfaction, vicarious trauma, and burnout, the respondents' ratings per subscale were summed. A subscale rating sum of 22 or less is equal to a subscale score of 43 or less which indicates low level. For a subscale rating sum between 23 and 41, the equivalent subscale score is around 50 which indicate average level. A subscale rating sum of 42 and above is equal to a subscale score of 57 or more which indicates high level.

The variable compassion fatigue had a total mean and standard deviation of (M= 3.784; SD= 4.592). The highest mean rating for the subscale was the statement "I get satisfaction from being able to help people" (M=4.18; SD=0.592) and the lowest mean rating was for the statement "I feel invigorated after working with those I help" (M=3.40; SD=0.931). The total score of compassion satisfaction is 37.84 with a standard deviation of 4.592 which correspond to a score equal to around 50. According to Stamm (2012), the average score is 50 (SD=10; alpha scale reliability=0.88). About 25% of the

respondents scored higher than 57 and about 25% scored below 43. If the respondents got a higher range, they most likely derive a good deal of professional satisfaction from their position. Subsequently, if the score is below 40, either the respondent may be experiencing problems with their job or there may be some other reasons. It may also be derived from satisfaction from activities other than their job.

Based on the results of the study, the score level of compassion satisfaction was at an average with a high risk for compassion fatigue which can still be prevented. If compassion is left unresolved, this often causes physical and emotional exhaustion and can significantly impair job performance (Sheppard, 2015). Nurse managers and administrators must pay attention to the scheduling and patient acuity experienced by their staff. Unrelenting self-sacrifice and/or prolonged exposure to trauma must be observed by the managers to identify manifestations of compassion fatigue that may be in the form of spiritual emptiness, a decreased sense of fulfillment, disconnectedness to people, lack of motivation, sensation of fatigue, personal and career dissatisfaction, and feelings of helplessness. Familiarity with the definition of compassion fatigue helps nurses identify this concept personally and among colleagues (Quinn, 2015). A better understanding about compassion fatigue is highly recommended to improve the overall well-being of health care practitioners and eventually to enhance patient care and retention within the profession.

The variable burnout had a total mean and standard deviation of (M=2.466; SD=0.5598). The highest mean rating was for the statement “I feel worn out because of my work as a nurse” (M=3.16; SD=0.824) and the lowest mean rating was for the statement “I am a very caring person” (M=1.89; SD=0.628). Total score for the burnout

scale was 24.66 with a standard deviation of 5.598 which corresponds to a score equal to around 50. The average score on the burnout scale is 50 (SD=10; alpha scale reliability=0.75). About 25% of the respondents scored above 57 and about 25% scored below 43 (Stamm, 2012). If the score is below 18, this reflects positive feelings about the respondents' ability to be effective in their work. Hence, if the score is above 57, the respondents may feel like they are not being effective in their position. The respondents may reflect a mood of having a bad day or they may need some time off according to Stamm (2012).

Consequently, results of the burnout scale showed an average level with a risk for burnout. Job dissatisfaction, which results to decreased productivity, loss of confidence and enthusiasm, and behavior changes may lead to typical stress-related symptoms if the situation is not addressed and stress continuous to accumulate (Rajeswari 2012). The five stages of burnout may escalate to mental and physical exhaustion that can further lead to four more stages: indifference, the feeling of failure as a professional, feeling of failure as a person, and feeling of emotional numbness (being "dead inside"). In addition, decrease in occupational well-being and increase in absenteeism, turnover, and illness are important problems for health care professionals (Adriaenssens, 2014). It is crucial to enhance job satisfaction and avoid burnout to maintain an adequate population of nurses which is vital for high-quality patient care. One must maintain a personal and professional lifestyle habit that will keep them healthy, engage in activities other than their profession, and connect with their family, friends, and colleagues. In addition, nurses should seek supportive relationships with

colleagues and ensure a work/life balance that fits their overall priorities (Rajeswari 2012).

Lastly, the variable vicarious trauma had a total mean and standard deviation of (M= 2.484; SD = 3.521). The highest mean rating was for the statement “I am preoccupied with more than one person I help” (M=3.26; SD=0.796) while lowest mean rating was for the statement “As a result of my helping, I have intrusive, frightening thoughts” (M=2.05; SD=0.975). The total score for vicarious trauma was 24.84 with a standard deviation of 3.521 which corresponds to a score equal to around 50. The average score on this subscale is 50 (SD=10; alpha scale reliability=0.81). About 25% of respondents scored below 43 and 25% scored above 57. If the score is above 57, there is a need to think about what part of the work may be traumatizing or if there is another reason for the elevated score. It does not necessarily mean that a problem exists but an indication that there is a need to examine how the respondents feel about work and their work environment. The needs of the supervisor, colleagues, or health care professionals and their situation when discussed may help (Stamm, 2012).

Result of the vicarious trauma scale was average level with a risk for vicarious trauma. If this was not prevented or left unresolved, an indication of high prevalence of vicarious trauma may contribute to emotional exhaustion and job separation of nurses which will further lead to job dissatisfaction or burnout (Rutledge and Dominguez-Gomez, 2011). In addition, a qualitative study of six social workers showed the importance of not bringing work at home or outside the workplace, spending time with family and friends, and talking with colleagues which helped them cope with vicarious trauma. At some point in their practice, they may experience vicarious trauma and managers can use this information to create policies and procedures to minimize its

impact (Fogel, 2015). Knowing and familiarizing oneself to the signs and symptoms of vicarious trauma and with the help of people around you can help minimize its occurrence.

Table 4. Relationship of Compassion Fatigue with Demographic, Personal and Work-Life Profile ($n=129$).

VARIABLES	χ^2	P value
Hospital Sector	15.920 ^a	0.000
Age	10.561 ^a	0.103
Gender	1.372 ^a	0.504
Years of Experience in the emergency room	1.576 ^a	0.954
Years of Experience as a Nurse	4.931 ^a	0.553
Relationship Status	5.646 ^a	0.059
Parent	9.107 ^a	0.011

Table 4. Continued...

VARIABLES	χ^2	P value
Hours worked per week	2.641 ^a	0.620
Shift work	2.800 ^a	0.247
Extra shift work	6.847 ^a	0.335
Physical Activity	7.445 ^a	0.282
Supportive work environment	5.515 ^a	0.480
Positive attitude towards work	19.597 ^a	0.001

* *correlation is significant at $p < 0.5$*

Table 4 shows the relationship of the respondents' compassion fatigue with their demographic, personal and work- life profile. Results of the study showed that there were significant relationships between compassion fatigue and hospital sector ($\chi^2=15.920^a$, $p > 0.000$), being a parent ($\chi^2=9.107^a$, $p>0.011$), relationship status ($\chi^2=5.646^a$, $p>0.059$), and positive attitude towards work ($\chi^2=19.597^a$, $p> 0.001$). In Lavado's (2011) study on the profile of private hospitals in the Philippines, majority of the hospitals in the country are privately owned and most of these hospitals are operating as profit institutions. On the other hand, even though there are more private hospitals in the Philippines, Filipinos who cannot afford services from private institutions would rather settle in the public or government owned hospitals. Aside from being more expensive, the current arrangement leads to overcrowding of tertiary facilities which results to longer waiting time for patients. This mismatch in the capability of tertiary facilities and the severity of cases they cater to lead to higher costs for seeking health care both for the institutions and the patients. The health system is therefore plagued with many challenges that undermine its efficiency (Lavado, 2010). Furthermore, Level 1 and 2 hospitals are well distributed compared to Level 3 and 4 hospitals. Majority of Level 3 and 4 hospitals are in urbanized areas and private hospitals have more cases of inpatient care. CALABARZON is one of the areas in the country with a high number of private hospitals. The result of the study showed that compassion fatigue was significant regardless if the nurse is working in a public or private institution ($\chi^2=15.920^a$, $p > 0.000$).

The respondents' relationship status showed significant relationship with compassion fatigue ($\chi^2=5.646^a$, $p>0.059$). According to a study, those who were

divorced are more at risk of developing compassion fatigue compared to single or widowed individuals (Chartterton, 2014). This supports the result that there is a significant relationship between compassion fatigue and relationship status. Chartterton's (2014) study concluded that those divorced or separated are more likely to experience compassion fatigue because they deal with the personal stressors of divorce/separation and their threshold for dealing with emotional, physical, social, and spiritual exhaustion may be lower which leads to a decline in caring for others (Chartterton, 2014). Further studies showed that the risk of compassion fatigue is associated with devotion behaviors and commitment towards the patient, exposure to multiple stressors, organizational challenges, and lack of self-care (Mahdie, 2017).

Being a parent was also significantly related to compassion fatigue ($\chi^2=9.107^a$, $p>0.011$). This result possibly stems from having no time for self-care as well as other circumstances related to having family and children. When parents focus on everyone else without practicing self-care, this may lead to destructive emotions, destructive feelings, and destructive behaviors (McCreight, 2013).

Demonstrating positive attitude towards their work in the emergency room had a significant relationship with compassion fatigue ($\chi^2=19.597^a$, $p> 0.001$). The Ecological Model for the Prevention of Compassion Fatigue identified social responsibilities such as social support, getting help, activism, and environmental responsibilities of re-evaluation of support system, education of social support system (Phillips, 2015). Majority of the research on compassion fatigue focused on nurse – patient relationships. However, workplace structural empowerment refers to “organizational factors that shape the work environment and also act as antecedents to nurse

empowerment, nurses' access to resources, support, opportunity, and information will impact their capacity for empowerment" (Rao, 2012).

Results of the study also showed that there were no significant relationships between compassion fatigue and age ($\chi^2 = 10.561^a$, $p > .05$), gender ($\chi^2 = 1.372^a$, $p > .05$), years of experience in the emergency room ($\chi^2 = 1.576^a$, $p > .05$), years of experience as a nurse ($\chi^2 = 4.931^a$, $p > .05$), hours worked per week ($\chi^2 = 2.641^a$, $p > .05$), shift work ($\chi^2 = 2.800^a$, $p > .05$), extra shift work ($\chi^2 = 6.847^a$, $p > .05$), physical activity ($\chi^2 = 7.445^a$, $p > .05$), and supportive work environment ($\chi^2 = 5.515^a$, $p > .05$). Contrary to the results, a study conducted in the Philippine Heart Center last 2015 showed that higher level of work stress lead to higher chance of vicarious trauma and the study also found out that male nurses appear more vulnerable compared to female nurses (Candano, 2015). In addition, Burtson and Stichler (2010) found a significant difference in compassion fatigue subscales according to age and nursing experience. Compassion fatigue was also negatively correlated with knowledge and skill, whereas knowledge and skill were positively correlated with the nurse's age and experience. Thus, an older and more experienced nurse has a higher degree of knowledge and skill with a lower risk for compassion fatigue. Another study with a different perspective included educational attainment in the variables. Although it was not part of the demographic data, the results implied that increasing the number of nurses with a bachelor's degree in an institution increases the likelihood of improved patient outcomes and can decrease levels of compassion fatigue (Smart, 2014). Thus, nurses with a bachelor's degree reported lower compassion satisfaction scores compared to nurses with associates or master's degrees. There were no significant differences in secondary traumatic stress

and burnout and educational preparation. Further research is needed to examine the combined relationship of educational preparation and entry into practice. Implications for nurse educators may also be discovered by further investigating the relationship between educational preparation and ProQOL.

Table 5. Relationship of Vicarious Trauma with Demographic, Personal and Work- Life Profile ($n=129$).

VARIABLES	χ^2	P value
Hospital Sector	2.822 ^a	0.093
Age	9.167 ^a	0.027
Gender	0.000 ^a	0.984
Years of Experience in the emergency room	5.544 ^a	0.136
Years of Experience as a Nurse	10.073 ^a	0.018
Relationship Status	0.209 ^a	0.648
Parent	1.515 ^a	0.218
Hours worked per week	0.929 ^a	0.628
Shift work	0.212 ^a	0.645
VARIABLES	χ^2	P value
Extra shift work	1.760 ^a	0.624
Physical Activity	4.179 ^a	0.243
Supportive work environment	5.714 ^a	0.126
Positive attitude towards work	2.791 ^a	0.248

* correlation is significant at $p<0.5$

Table 5 shows the relationship of the respondents' vicarious trauma with their demographic, personal, and work-life profile. Results show that there was a significant relationship between vicarious trauma, age ($\chi^2 = 9.167^a$, $p > .05$) and years of experience as a nurse ($\chi^2 = 10.073^a$, $p > .05$). Age had a significant relationship with vicarious trauma because age can be affected by the length of exposure to trauma, experience in life, and their level of maturity such as how they handle or cope with the situation. Similar to the results in Table 5, there were studies conducted confirming the significant relationship between age and vicarious trauma. A research study about 50-years and older nurses showed that they scored higher on compassion satisfaction and lower on the vicarious trauma and burnout scale compared with the younger nurses. In an article published by Lippincott Solutions (2015), Tara Sacco, a visiting Assistant Professor from St. John Fisher College and also a clinical nurse specialist, was cited saying that the older nurses have more professional and life experiences and therefore are better prepared to cope with the challenges of critical care nursing. The relationship between age and ProQOL has been also examined by other researchers.

The variable years of experience as a nurse ($\chi^2 = 10.073^a$, $p > .05$) also had a significant relationship with vicarious trauma. Studies have shown that secondary traumatic stress also known as vicarious trauma is a negative change that happens to health practitioners overtime as they witness other people's suffering and need. Vicarious trauma is the process of change that happens because of caring for other people who have been hurt and the feeling of commitment or responsibility to help them. Overtime, this process can lead to changes in the psychological, physical, and spiritual well-being. Despite this, anyone who has extended contact with trauma victims

or traumatic materials is at risk of vicarious trauma as noted by Wasco and Campbell (2002). This includes legal professionals, health professionals, researchers, and educators. Another research study in Europe correlated age and work and concluded that as workers age, their physical and mental abilities tend to decline and the occurrence of accidents and diseases likewise increases with age. The study highlighted that as workers continue to age their work ability decreases. However, there are also contradicting studies to the previously mentioned literature. In a study about elders who work in heavy industries, results showed that there was a difference in physical ability among the elderly workers (age 50 years old or older) which was relatively smaller than young workers (aged 39 or younger) (Chung, 2015).

Table 5 also shows there were no significant relationships between vicarious trauma and the hospital sector ($\chi^2= 2.822^a$, $p>.05$), gender ($\chi^2= 0.000^a$, $p>.05$), years of experience in emergency room ($\chi^2= 5.544^a$, $p>.05$), relationship status ($\chi^2= 0.209^a$, $p>.05$), parent ($\chi^2= 1.515^a$, $p>.05$), hours worked per week ($\chi^2= 0.929^a$, $p>.05$), shift work ($\chi^2= 0.212^a$, $p>.05$), extra shift work ($\chi^2= 1.760^a$, $p>.05$), physical activity ($\chi^2= 4.179^a$, $p>.05$), supportive work environment ($\chi^2= 5.714^a$, $p>.05$), and positive towards work ($\chi^2= 2.791^a$, $p>.05$). Limited studies have been found and were supported by a study conducted by Jone-Maning (2016). An independent t-test was conducted to determine whether gender had a significant difference on any of the key variables included in the current study. Female respondents ($M=11.71$; $SD=14.60$) were found to score significantly higher than males ($M=106.43$; $SD=13.87$) but there were no significant differences between male and female on any of the other measured variables (all p values were greater than 0.05). This finding was similar to available dissertations

about the correlation between demographic data and vicarious trauma where one study reported that there were no significant relationships with work-related experience and demographic profile but compassion satisfaction was found to be the only unique predictor of alliance ratings. In addition, the study also reported a significant relationship between vicarious trauma and years of experience. The hierarchal regression analyses showed that perceived alliances were stronger for therapists who had been working relatively longer in the specific field. These were therapists who work with clients who committed sexual abuse.

Table 6. Relationship of Burnout with Demographic, Personal and Work- Life Profile ($n=129$).

VARIABLES	χ^2	P value
Hospital Sector	2.822 ^a	0.093
Age	9.167 ^a	0.027
Gender	0.000 ^a	0.984
Years of Experience in the emergency room	5.544 ^a	0.136
Years of Experience as a Nurse	10.073 ^a	0.018
Relationship Status	0.209 ^a	0.648
Parent	1.515 ^a	0.218
Hours worked per week	0.929 ^a	0.628
Shift work	0.212 ^a	0.645
Extra shift work	1.760 ^a	0.624
VARIABLES	χ^2	P value
Physical Activity	4.179 ^a	0.243

Supportive work environment	5.714 ^a	0.126
Positive attitude towards work	2.791 ^a	0.248

* correlation is significant at $p < 0.5$

Table 6 shows the relationship of burnout with demographic, personal, and work-life profile. Results show that there were significant relationships between burnout, age ($\chi^2 = 9.167^a$, $p > .05$), and years of experience as a nurse ($\chi^2 = 10.073^a$, $p > .05$). This result was similar to a study conducted by Asonza (2019) titled Factors Affecting Millennial Nursing Personnel Retention in Rizal Medical Center: A Basis for Improving the Nursing Workforce. Currently, the millennial generation has surpassed the baby boomers as the largest living generation. This generation has started to saturate the work force of companies and institutions, yet organizations find it difficult to retain them at the same time. Findings revealed that there was a high level of millennial nursing personnel retention and a significant relationship between employee retention and their organization commitment, job burnout, and organizational environment. In the study, significant predictors of burnout included lack of meaningful recognition, nurses with more years of experience, and nurses in the millennial generation (ages 21 – 33 years) while those who received meaningful recognition were the baby boomers generation (ages 50 – 65 years). Nurses with fewer years of experience also significantly predicted compassion satisfaction (Kelly, 2015). This study adds a potential explanation for the fast turnover of nurses from the millennial generation who leave their positions with limited years of experience.

Another study showed that there was a significant relationship between age and burnout among the population of a Swedish county. Results reported a high level of burnout common among aging workers compared with middle aged workers (Ahola, 2014). Hence, a meta-analysis of employee burnout and its relationship with age and years of experience, and appropriateness of approach in addressing the employee burnout depend on whether age or years of experience are factors related to burnout. Although Brewer (2004) noted that the result suggested a small negative correlation between employee age and emotional exhaustion, a component of burnout, and a small negative correlation between years of experience in the field of exhaustion.

Table 6 also shows there were no significant relationships between burnout, hospital sector ($\chi^2 = 2.822^a$, $p > .05$), gender ($\chi^2 = 0.000^a$, $p > .05$), years of experience in the emergency room ($\chi^2 = 5.544^a$, $p > .05$), relationship status ($\chi^2 = 0.209^a$, $p > .05$), parent ($\chi^2 = 1.515^a$, $p > .05$), hours worked per week ($\chi^2 = 0.929^a$, $p > .05$), shift work ($\chi^2 = 0.212^a$, $p > .05$), extra shift work ($\chi^2 = 1.760^a$, $p > .05$), physical activity ($\chi^2 = 4.179^a$, $p > .05$), supportive environment ($\chi^2 = 5.714^a$, $p > .05$), and positive attitude towards work ($\chi^2 = 2.791^a$, $p > .05$). Despite having no significant relationship with gender, El-Bar (2013) conducted a study among family physicians and results showed an increased risk for burnout associated with females. This finding contradicts the results found in Table 6. Another research about years of experience of resident physicians in the emergency room showed that factors such as shifts times, duration of each shift, little access to nonmedical personnel, the quality of emergency conditions, lack of enough break times during the shift, the extent of theoretical knowledge, the lack of practical skills required for professionals in the field, emergency patients' conditions, conflicts with moral issues,

workload, and professional discipline were physical conditions in the emergency room that caused problems for them. The findings showed lack of control over work schedule and planning, organizing, and hard working conditions as problematic for the respondents (Kamaloo, 2017). In addition, a study conducted in Iran last 2017 showed that burnout had a significant relationship with relationship status. Married nursing staffs were found to have lower level of burnout compared with single nurses and there was a correlation between age and job satisfaction. Therefore, job burnout was directly correlated with job stress while job burnout was negatively correlated with job satisfaction. It was concluded that plans to reduce burnout of the emergency nursing staff are necessary (Tavakoli. 2018).

Chapter V

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendation

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, conclusion, and recommendation based from the results in Chapter IV of the study.

Summary

The main objective of the study was to describe the level of awareness and determine the level of risk of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among

emergency room department nurses from selected tertiary hospitals in the province of Laguna and its correlation to demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment. Specifically, the study was conducted to determine the emergency room nurses' level of compassion fatigue awareness score, level of vicarious trauma awareness score, and level of burnout awareness score. The study also identified if there was a significant relationship among the following: a.) compassion fatigue with demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment, b.) vicarious trauma with demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment, and c.) burnout with demographic data, work environment, client environment, and personal environment.

1. A total of 129 respondents participated in this study. Majority of them came from private hospitals as opposed to public hospitals (67.4, 32.6). Most of the respondents were aged 20 – 29 years to 30 – 39 years old (55.0, 31.0). In addition, there were more female respondents than the males (59.7, 40.3) and most of them were also single as opposed to married or having common law relationships (79, 50). In relation to this, the number of respondents with no children was higher compared to those with a child (58.9, 41.1). There was a large difference in terms of years of experience of the respondents in the emergency room ranging from 0 – 5 years and 6 – 10 years (70.5, 16.3). Therefore, most of them have worked in the emergency room from 0 – 5 years only. In terms of number of years in the nursing profession, many of them have worked from 0 -5 years to 6 -10 years (42.6, 31.8). In addition, majority of the

respondents were working 32 hours or more per week. Most of the respondents rendered overtime which lasted for 16 hours or less (75.2, 24) and 113 out of 129 respondents did shift work (87.6). In connection with this, majority of the respondents worked an extra shift more than once per month (55.8). Nurses in the emergency room also rarely engaged in physical activities or at most 3 days per month (48.1, 30.2). The respondents also strongly agreed that their department work environment was supportive (50.4, 24) and their colleagues demonstrated a positive attitude towards the work they do (58.9, 25.6).

2. The respondents' thoughts about compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout showed that there was a high number of nurses that have not heard of the terms or were not aware of compassion fatigue and vicarious trauma (49.6, 49.6) while nurses in the emergency room have somewhat heard and were aware of the term burnout (93). Majority of the respondents' workplace did not offer any program or assistance in dealing with compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout while some were not sure or aware of the existence of such programs (59.7, 32.6). Hence, the respondents perceived the issue as very important to somewhat important in their workplace (78.3, 18.6).
3. The compassion fatigue total mean and standard deviation were (M=3.784, SD=4.592). Total score of compassion satisfaction was 37.84 with a standard deviation of 4.592 which correspond to their score as equal to around 50 and compassion satisfaction level was average. Vicarious trauma had a total mean and standard deviation of M=2.484 and SD=3.521. Total score of vicarious trauma was 24.84 with a standard deviation of 3.521 which correspond to their

score equal to around 50 and vicarious trauma scale level was average. Lastly, burnout had a total mean and standard deviation of $M=24.66$ and $SD=5.598$. Total score of the burnout scale was 24.66 with a standard deviation of 5.598 which correspond to their score equal to around 50 and burnout scale level was average.

4. The study also showed that there were significant relationships between compassion fatigue and hospital sector ($\chi^2 = 15.920^a$, $p > .05$), parent ($\chi^2 = 9.107^a$, $p > .05$), relationship status ($\chi^2=5.646^a$, $p>0.059$), and positive attitude towards work ($\chi^2= 19.597^a$, $p>.05$). For vicarious trauma, there were significant relationships between vicarious trauma and age ($\chi^2 = 9.167^a$, $p>.05$) and years of experience as a nurse ($\chi^2 = 10.073^a$, $p>.05$). Lastly, there were significant relationships between burnout and age ($\chi^2 = 9.167^a$, $p>.05$) and years of experience as a nurse ($\chi^2 = 10.073^a$, $p>.05$).

Conclusion

Overall, majority of the study's participants were female nurses working in private hospitals, aged 20 – 29 years old, with 0 – 5 years of experience in the emergency room department and likewise 0 – 5 years' experience in the nursing profession. More than fifty percent (50%) of the respondents were single and without a child. Generally, nurses in the emergency room worked for 32 hours or more and did shifting work. Most of the respondents in the emergency room rendered extra shift work or overtime more than once per month which lead to their rare engagement in physical activities. Additionally, nurses agreed that their working environment was supportive and their colleagues demonstrated a positive attitude towards the work they do.

The respondents also reported that they have not heard of the term compassion fatigue and vicarious trauma, therefore, the workplace needs to offer programs or assistance to deal with compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout. Majority of the nurses were aware of the term burnout and considered the three terms as important issues in their workplace.

The level of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout among nurses in the emergency room department of selected tertiary hospitals in Laguna was average. Therefore, the respondents were at risk but did not experience compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, or burnout when the study was conducted. However, if left unresolved, compassion fatigue which is the combined negative impact of vicarious trauma and burnout or may lead to vicarious trauma or burnout (Bouchard, 2016).

The researcher also concluded that there were significant relationships between compassion fatigue and the hospital sector, parent, relationship status, and positive attitude. Therefore, nurses who worked in a private hospital, who were single, without a child, and with colleagues that demonstrated a positive attitude towards work had a significant relationship with compassion fatigue. This conclusion was similar with the findings on vicarious trauma and burnout. The study also showed that age and years of experience as a nurse had significant relationships between vicarious trauma and burnout. Therefore, nurses aged 20 -29 years old and those with 0 – 5 years' experience in the nursing profession had significant relationships to vicarious trauma and burnout.

Recommendations

Given the results and implications of the present study, the following recommendations were drawn:

To Nursing Practice and Research

1. There may be a need to have more local research on compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout not only in the emergency room but also in all departments that may be at risk of having compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.
2. A better understanding on compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout is highly recommended to improve the overall well-being of health care practitioners and ultimately to enhance patient care and retention within the profession
3. Evidenced-based research regarding programs offered to prevent compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout for nurses or health care providers exposed to risk factors should be conducted.

To Nursing Administration

1. There is a need for support from the hospital administration and medical and nursing services to achieve work-life balance for the nurses.
2. The hospital management should address compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout in their hospitals. Programs, activities such as team building or company outing, and support groups may alleviate the risk and presence of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.
3. Education and in-service training that include compassion satisfaction, coping strategies, stress management, relaxation techniques, and self-care intervention are highly recommended to prevent compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout.

4. Provision of equal distribution of workload and management of immediate response to incidents.

To Nursing Education

1. The study will serve as a good reference of an evidenced – based research which may be used in lectures. Awareness of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma, and burnout leads to lesser risk of acquiring these and a higher chance for prevention

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: Questionnaire/ Tool for Data Collection

A. Demographic, Personal and Work-life Questions

Demographic, Personal and Work-life Questions	
Hospital sector?	<input type="radio"/> Public hospital <input type="radio"/> Private hospital
How old are you?	<input type="radio"/> 20-29 <input type="radio"/> 30-39 <input type="radio"/> 40-49 <input type="radio"/> Above 50
Gender?	<input type="radio"/> Female <input type="radio"/> Male
How long do you work on your current unit?	<input type="radio"/> 0-5 years <input type="radio"/> 6-10 years <input type="radio"/> 11-15 years <input type="radio"/> 15 years or more
How long have you been a nurse?	<input type="radio"/> 0-5 years <input type="radio"/> 6-10 years <input type="radio"/> 11-15 years <input type="radio"/> 16 years or more
What is your relationship status?	<input type="radio"/> Single <input type="radio"/> Married or common law <input type="radio"/> Separated, divorced, or widowed <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to say
Are you a parent?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
Hours worked/week?	<input type="radio"/> 16 or less <input type="radio"/> 17-31 <input type="radio"/> 32 or more

Do you work shift work?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
How often do you work an extra shift?	<input type="radio"/> More than once per month <input type="radio"/> Once every 1-3 months <input type="radio"/> Rarely <input type="radio"/> Never
How often do you engage in physical activity?	<input type="radio"/> Frequently (at least 3 days per week) <input type="radio"/> Often (at least 3 days per month) <input type="radio"/> Rarely <input type="radio"/> Never
Please answer the following questions indicating how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.	
The department I work on is a supportive work environment	<input type="radio"/> Strongly agree <input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Neutral <input type="radio"/> Disagree <input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree
My colleagues demonstrate a positive attitude towards the work we do	<input type="radio"/> Strongly agree <input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Neutral <input type="radio"/> Disagree <input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree

Thoughts about Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma and Burnout	
Prior to being asked to participate in this research study, have you ever heard of the term "Compassion Fatigue?"	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Not sure

<p>Prior to being asked to participate in this research study, have you ever heard of the term “Vicarious Trauma?”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Not sure
<p>Prior to being asked to participate in this research study, have you ever heard of the term “Burnout?”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Not sure
<p>Does your workplace offer any program or assistance in dealing with Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious trauma or burnout?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Not sure <p>If yes, please specify the program:</p>
<p>How important an issue do you feel compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout is in your workplace?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Very important <input type="radio"/> Somewhat important <input type="radio"/> Not important <input type="radio"/> Not sure

APPENDIX B. Professional Quality of Life (ProQol, 2012)

PROFESSIONAL QUALITY OF LIFE SCALE (PROQOL) COMPASSION SATISFACTION AND COMPASSION FATIGUE

Below are some questions about your experiences, both positive and negative, as a Nurse. Consider each of the following questions about you and your current work situation. Select the number that honestly reflects how frequently you experienced these things in the last 30 days.

1=Never 2=Rarely 3=Sometimes 4=Often 5=Very Often

- _____ 1. I am happy.
- _____ 2. I am preoccupied with more than one person I help.
- _____ 3. I get satisfaction from being able to help people.
- _____ 4. I feel connected to others.
- _____ 5. I jump or am startled by unexpected sounds.
- _____ 6. I feel invigorated after working with those I help.
- _____ 7. I find it difficult to separate my personal life from my life as a nurse.
- _____ 8. I am not as productive at work because I am losing sleep over traumatic experiences of a person I help.
- _____ 9. I think that I might have been affected by the traumatic stress of those I help.
- _____ 10. I feel trapped by my job as a nurse.
- _____ 11. Because of my helping, I have felt "on edge" about various things.
- _____ 12. I like my work as a nurse.

- _____ 13. I feel depressed because of the traumatic experiences of the people I help.
- _____ 14. I feel as though I am experiencing the trauma of someone I have helped.
- _____ 15. I have beliefs that sustain me.
- _____ 16. I am pleased with how I am able to keep up with helping techniques and protocols.
- _____ 17. I am the person I always wanted to be.
- _____ 18. My work makes me feel satisfied.
- _____ 19. I feel worn out because of my work as a nurse.
- _____ 20. I have happy thoughts and feelings about those I help and how I could help them.
- _____ 21. I feel overwhelmed because my case work load seems endless.
- _____ 22. I believe I can make a difference through my work.
- _____ 23. I avoid certain activities or situations because they remind me of frightening experiences of the people I help.
- _____ 24. I am proud of what I can do to help.
- _____ 25. As a result of my helping, I have intrusive, frightening thoughts.
- _____ 26. I feel "bogged down" by the system.
- _____ 27. I have thoughts that I am a "success" as a nurse.
- _____ 28. I can't recall important parts of my work with trauma victims.
- _____ 29. I am a very caring person.
- _____ 30. I am happy that I chose to do this work

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APPENDIX C: Professional Quality of Life (ProQol, 2012) Tagalog Version

Panukat ng Kapaguran sa Pagkahabag at ang Kasiyahan sa Pagkahabag Kapag ikaw ay tumulong sa tao, mayroon kang tuwirang pakikitungo sa kanilang buhay. At iyong matutuklasan, ang iyong pagkahabag sa iyong mga natulungan ay makakaapekto sa iyo positibo at negatibong paraan. Sa ibaba ay mga katanungan tungkol sa iyong mga karanasan, pareho itong positibo at negatibo bilang isang Nars. Ipagpalagay na bawat katanungan ay tungkol sa iyo at sa iyong kasalukuyang sitwasyon sa iyong trabaho. Piliin ang numero nang may katapatan na sumasalamin gaano mo kadalas nararanasan ang mga bagay na ito sa nakalipas na 30 araw.

1= Hindi 2= Madalang 3= Paminsan-minsan 4= May Kadalasan 5= Madalas

- _____ 1. Ako ay masaya.
- _____ 2. Ako ay totoong abala sa mga taong tinutulungan ko
- _____ 3. Ako ay nasisiyahan kapag nakakatulung ako sa tao
- _____ 4. Nadarama ko na may kaugnayan ako sa iba
- _____ 5. Ako ay napapatalon o nagugulat sa mga hindi inaasahang tunog
- _____ 6. Nakadarama ako ng kasiglahan/kalakasan pagkatapos kung makatrabaho ang aking mga natulungan
- _____ 7. Nahihirapan ako na paghiwalayin ang sarili kung buhay sa buhay ko bilang isang nars
- _____ 8. Hindi ako kasing produktibo sa trabaho dahil sa kakulangan sa tulog sa mga labis na tromang nararanasan ng mga tao na aking tinutulungan

- _____ 9. Satingin ko, maaari akong maapektuhan sa tindi ng troma ng aking mga tinutulungan
- _____ 10. Nakadarama ako na bitag ako ng aking trabaho bilang nars.
- _____ 11. Dahil sa aking pagtulong, narandaman kong higit ako sa ibat ibang bagay
- _____ 12. Gusto ko ang aking trabaho bilang nars
- _____ 13. Nakadarama ako ng kalungkutan dahil sa mga tromang karanasan ng mga taong aking tinutulungan
- _____ 14. Pakiramdam ko nararanasan ko ang tromang naranasan ng mga taong aking tinutulungan
- _____ 15. May paniniwala akong may aalalay/hahawak sa akin
- _____ 16. Ako ay nagagalak kung paano ko napapanatili ang pamamaraan at protocol sa pagtulong
- _____ 17. Ako ang taong lagging gusting maging ako
- _____ 18. Ang aking trabaho ay nagbibigay kasiyahan sa akin
- _____ 19. Nakadarama ako ng hapong-hapo/pagod na pagod ako dahil sa trabaho ko bilang nars
- _____ 20. Mayroon akong masiyang pag-iisip at damdamin sa mga natulungan ko at kung papaano ko pa sila matutulungan
- _____ 21. Nakadarama akong kapuspusan dahil sa tambak na trabaho ng parang walang katapusan
- _____ 22. Naniniwala ako na nagkakaroon ako ng pagkakaiba sa pamamagitan ng aking trabaho

- _____23. Umiwas ako sa mga tiyak na aktibidad o sitwasyon dahil pinapaalalahanan ako sa mga nakakatakot na karanasan ng mga taong aking natulungan
- _____24. Ipinagmamapuri ko kung ano ang aking nagagawa sa pagtulong
- _____25. Bilang resulta sa aking pagtulong, ako ay pinapasukan ng nakakatakot na pag-iisip
- _____26. Ako ay nakadarama ng pagbagsak ng sistema
- _____27. Naiisip ko na ako ay matagumpay bilang nars
- _____28. Hindi ko maalala ang mga importanting bahagi ng aking trabaho sa mga may biktima ng troma
- _____29. Ako ay maarugang tao
- _____30. Masaya ako na napili kong gawin ang trabahong ito

APPENDIX D. Consent Form for Participation in a Research Study

Compassion Fatigue, Vicarious Trauma and Burnout among Nurses in Emergency Room Departments of Selected Tertiary Hospitals in Laguna

Description of the research and your participation

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by Regine Karla P. Bagalanon from University of the Philippines Open University. The general objective of the study is to explore the experiences, symptoms, and effects of compassion fatigue among emergency room nurses. Specifically, to determine the level of compassion fatigue among nurses working in emergency room department, signs and symptoms of compassion fatigue and to determine the contributing factors that may result in compassion fatigue. In addition, this study will contribute to the researcher's completion of her post-graduate or master's degree research.

This study of a survey forms by Stamm, 2010 Professional Quality of Life also known as ProQol 2012 and questionnaire that will administered to individual respondents in Selected Tertiary Hospitals within Laguna. Participation in this study will require approximately fifteen minutes of your time. The research does not perceive more than minimal risk arising from your involvement with this study. Potential benefits from participation includes awareness of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout, determining the signs and symptoms, and how to balance the nurse's well-being.

The result of this research will be presented at University of the Philippines Open University. While individual responses will be obtained and recorded anonymously and kept in the strictest form of confidentiality. Participation on this research is entirely voluntary. You are free to choose not to participate. Should you choose to participate, you can withdraw anytime without consequences of any kind.

Risk and discomforts

This study involves no risks/ or discomfort on the part of respondents.

Potential Benefits

The result will be used as a baseline and guideline assessment of compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma and burnout among nurses.

Protection of Confidentiality

Your identity will not be revealed if in any publication that might result from this study. The result of your answer will be sealed, and protection of privacy is our thrust.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation on this research is voluntary. If you choose not to participate, you may withdraw your consent to participate at any time. You will not be penalized in any way should you decide not to participate or to withdraw at any point from this study.

Contact information

If you have any question or concerns during the time of your participation in this study, or after its completion or if you would like to receive a copy of the final result of this study, please contact:

Regine Karla P. Bagalanon, RN
Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines Open University
Mobile No. +639088894920

reginekarlabagalanon@yahoo.com.ph

Queenie Ridulme RN, MAN
Faculty in Charge
University of the Philippines Open University
Queenie.ridulme@upou.edu.ph

Consent

I have read and understand what is being requested of me as a respondent in this study. I freely consent to participate on this research in completion of researcher's requirements.

_____ / _____

(Sign of Respondent over printed Name) Date

_____ / _____

(Sign of Principal Investigator) Date

A copy of consent form should be given to you.

APPENDIX E: Letter for Chief Directors and Ethical Board Committee of Tertiary Hospitals in Laguna

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES OPEN UNIVERSITY
Los Baños, Laguna

January 2019

Dear Madam,

Greetings of Peace and Prosperity!

I, Regine Karla Bagalanon a graduating student of University of the Philippines Open University under the Master of Arts in Nursing, is conducting a research study entitled **COMPASSION FATIGUE, VICARIOUS TRAUMA AND BURNOUT AMONG NURSES IN EMERGENCY ROOM DEPARTMENT OF SELECTED TERTIARY HOSPITALS IN LAGUNA.**

In this regard, I would like to request from your good office to allow me to conduct my study to emergency room nurses of your institution by answering the attached questionnaire that will take fifteen minutes of their time. Rest assured that the gathered data will be strictly for research purposes only and will be kept outmost confidential. Should you wish to have a copy of my research result, it would be an honor to present my research dissertation and provide a copy for you.

I am looking forward to your favorable response.

Very truly yours,

Regine Karla P. Bagalanon
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Noted By:

